

Efficient Sequential Coupling Technique for the Simulation of Hydro-Mechanical Interaction in Rock Engineering

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ABSTRACT: The coupling of fluid flow and deformation in deformable porous media has started to receive wide attention in rock engineering. Acknowledging this hydro-mechanical (H-M) interaction is essential for the safe design of geo-engineering structures in saturated ground. Explicit coupling techniques have been the most attractive approach to use for simulating the H-M interaction, yet, the techniques are conditionally stable and require small time steps, affecting their efficiency for long-term simulations. To remove these restrictions, an unconditionally stable alternating direction explicit (ADE) scheme could be used to solve the flow problem. However, the standard ADE scheme is only moderately accurate and is restricted to uniform grids, thus impractical for large-scale domains. This paper presents the derivation of a novel high-order ADE scheme for non-uniform grids to solve the flow problem. The flow solutions are then sequentially coupled with a geomechanical simulator in the computer code Fast Lagrangian Analysis of Continua (FLAC). Validations based on Terzaghi's consolidation problems show that the new sequential coupling technique reduces simulation runtimes by 40% of FLAC's basic scheme without numerical instability and with average errors of 6% for pore pressure and 0.4% for displacement. The new coupling technique also results in satisfactory H-M response of a permeable tunnel under surface loading and reduces the computer runtime by 24%.

1. INTRODUCTION

Biot's theory of poroelasticity (Biot, 1941) has been prominently employed in rock mechanics to understand the coupled response of fluid flow and deformation in deformable porous media (i.e., soils and rocks). Acknowledging this coupled hydro-mechanical (H-M) interaction is essential for the safe design of geo-engineering structures built above and under saturated ground such as embankment and tunnels. Consolidation and subsidence are the most common examples of the two-way coupled interaction in which fluid flow affects deformation and vice versa (Gutierrez and Lewis, 2002; Neuzil, 2003; Wang, 2000).

Various numerical coupling techniques have been developed to solve the coupled Biot's equations that govern the response of the fluid (the flow problem) and the solid (the geomechanical problem). The flow problem is represented by the mass balance equation, which is based on Biot's theory, and the geomechanical problem is represented by Terzaghi's effective stress principle, equilibrium condition, constitutive law, and displacement to strain compatibility relations (Gutierrez and Lewis, 2002).

Among the various coupling techniques, the explicitly coupled approach is the most attractive to use. The explicit technique is not only simple to implement, but also less time-consuming in building the separate geomechanical and fluid flow codes for solving the coupled equations, while still able to capture the desired coupled interactions. Unfortunately, the technique comes at a price: it is *conditionally* stable. The explicit nature of the technique requires that small time step sizes must be used to maintain numerical stability and accuracy, placing a strong limitation on the technique. Consequently, the efficiency of computer runtime for an explicit-type coupling technique cannot be fully exploited for large-scale and long-term H-M simulations that may need enormously long computation time, such as subsidence induced by hydro-carbon production in an oil field and consolidation due to tunneling in saturated ground.

The widely used explicit finite difference (FD) code for coupled fluid flow and geomechanical computation called Fast Lagrangian Analysis of Continua or FLAC is also conditionally stable in that it has restrictions on the time step for its flow calculation (Itasca, 2011a). Unlike the fluid flow effect that takes place over a considerable amount of time, the geomechanical calculation in FLAC is not of particular concern because the geomechanical

effects of a coupled problem occur almost instantaneously during the small time step.

2. THE NEED FOR AN EFFICIENT SEQUENTIAL COUPLING TECHNIQUE

To remove the time step restriction in an explicit coupling technique, one proposed method is to develop an *unconditionally* stable fluid flow scheme that can be sequentially coupled with an existing geomechanical simulator (e.g., FLAC). The alternating direction explicit (ADE) scheme is one such scheme. In the ADE scheme, two explicit FD equations are executed simultaneously to solve a target point in two physical directions: one in a forward sweep and the other in a reverse sweep.

In the ADE scheme, to solve a target point (x_i, y_j) at the current time level $(n + 1)$, both sweeping procedures use a combination of the solutions from the previous time level (n) and the current time level $(n + 1)$. The difference, however, is indicated by the location of the solutions from the current time level $(n + 1)$ with respect to the location of the target point in each sweep.

In the forward sweep (Fig. 1a), the calculation to solve the target point marches upward in an ascending order of x and y in which it uses the solutions from the current time level $(n + 1)$ located *behind* the target point. On the other hand, in the reverse sweep (Fig. 1b), the calculation to solve the same target point marches downward in a descending order of x and y in which it uses the solutions from the current time level $(n + 1)$ located *ahead* of the target point. In this way, the explicitness of the scheme is preserved while improving the stability of the scheme. This is the merit of the ADE scheme.

To get the mathematical sense of how the ADE scheme works, consider a fluid diffusion equation in Eq. (1).

$$\frac{\partial p}{\partial t} = \frac{\partial^2 p}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 p}{\partial y^2} \quad (1)$$

Barakat and Clark (1966) used the ADE scheme to solve Eq. (1) in the forward and reverse sweeps as written in Eqs. (2) and (3), respectively.

$$u_{i,j}^{n+1} = a u_{i,j}^n + b(u_{i-1,j}^{n+1} + u_{i+1,j}^n) + c(u_{i,j-1}^{n+1} + u_{i,j+1}^n) \quad (2)$$

$$v_{i,j}^{n+1} = a v_{i,j}^n + b(v_{i-1,j}^n + v_{i+1,j}^{n+1}) + c(v_{i,j-1}^n + v_{i,j+1}^{n+1}) \quad (3)$$

where

$$a = \frac{1 - \Delta t(1/\Delta x^2 + 1/\Delta y^2)}{1 - \Delta t(1/\Delta x^2 + 1/\Delta y^2)} = \frac{1 - \lambda}{1 + \lambda} \quad (4)$$

$$b = \frac{\Delta t}{\Delta x^2} \frac{1}{1 + \lambda}, \quad c = \frac{\Delta t}{\Delta y^2} \frac{1}{1 + \lambda}$$

The final solution is the average of the solutions from the two sweeps as shown in Eq. (5).

$$p_{i,j}^{n+1} = \frac{1}{2}(u_{i,j}^{n+1} + v_{i,j}^{n+1}) \quad (5)$$

Fig. 1. Illustration of (a) forward and (b) reverse sweeps in the standard ADE scheme (Prasetyo, 2017).

Despite its unconditional stability, the standard ADE scheme has three major drawbacks: (1) it is only moderately accurate (second-order accurate in time and space); (2) it is only valid for uniform grid sizes (same Δx and Δy for the entire grid model); (3) it can only be used for plane strain conditions. With these drawbacks, the standard ADE scheme will encounter substantial difficulties when it is coupled with a geomechanical simulator to solve a H-M coupled problem.

Its low-order accuracy will become a major challenge when a large time step size is desired for an efficient H-M simulation but high numerical accuracy is still retained. Likewise, the strong limitation on the grid sizes will make the standard ADE scheme even less practical for solving large-scale coupled problems in which the FD model is usually arranged with gradually increasing grid size toward the far-field boundaries. More importantly, it cannot be used for solving coupled problems under axisymmetric conditions such as the axisymmetric consolidation of shallow foundation and deep tunnel in saturated ground.

Therefore, the objective of this paper is to eliminate the first two drawbacks by presenting a new high-order ADE scheme capable of solving the plane strain fluid flow problem in a non-uniform grid configuration. The new

ADE scheme for solving axisymmetric fluid flow problems is derived in Prasetyo (2017). The fluid flow solution resulting from this novel scheme is then sequentially coupled with the existing geomechanical simulator in FLAC. Because the time step restriction is removed, the H-M simulation can be performed with less computation time and without numerical instability and yet still retain high numerical accuracy.

3. DERIVATION OF HIGH-ORDER ADE SCHEME

The governing equations for coupled fluid flow and geomechanical interactions consist of the mass balance equation, which governs the hydraulic response of the fluid, and the momentum balance equation, which governs the geomechanical response of the porous medium.

According to Biot's theory of poroelasticity (Biot, 1941), the responses of the fluid (pore pressure) and the solid (total stress) are related to the changes in fluid content (ζ) and volumetric strain (ε_{vol}) of the porous medium.

This relation can be written as

$$\frac{\partial p}{\partial t} = M \left(\frac{\partial \zeta}{\partial t} - \alpha \frac{\partial \varepsilon_{\text{vol}}}{\partial t} \right) \quad (6)$$

$$\sigma_{ij} + \alpha p \delta_{ij} = 2G \varepsilon_{ij} + \left(K - \frac{2}{3} G \right) \varepsilon_{\text{vol}} \delta_{ij} \quad (7)$$

In this paper, the adopted sequential coupling technique freezes the mechanical deformation in Eq. (6) during fluid flow calculation ($\delta \varepsilon_{\text{vol}} = 0$). Hence, Biot's equation for fluid flow is only represented by a fluid-diffusion equation as shown in Eq. (8).

$$f = c_v \left(\frac{\partial^2 p}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 p}{\partial y^2} \right) \quad (8)$$

where $f = \partial p / \partial t$ and c_v is the coefficient of consolidation defined as $c_v = kM$, k is the mobility coefficient defined as $k = k_H / \gamma_w$, k_H is the hydraulic conductivity, γ_w is the unit weight of fluid and M is the Biot modulus.

To develop the proposed high-order ADE schemes for non-uniform grid, the second order derivatives in Eq. (8) must be approximated to the fourth-order accuracy. Consider a general non-uniform FD grid that consists of four quadrilateral elements as shown in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2. Illustration of non-uniform FD grid.

Writing the Taylor series expansion for $p_{i+1,j}$ and $p_{i-1,j}$ to the fourth-order gives

$$p_{i+1,j} = p_{i,j} + \Delta x_+ \left(\frac{\partial p}{\partial x} \right) + \frac{1}{2} \Delta x_+^2 \left(\frac{\partial^2 p}{\partial x^2} \right) + \frac{1}{6} \Delta x_+^3 \left(\frac{\partial^3 p}{\partial x^3} \right) + \frac{1}{24} \Delta x_+^4 \left(\frac{\partial^4 p}{\partial x^4} \right) + \dots \quad (9)$$

$$p_{i-1,j} = p_{i,j} - \Delta x_- \left(\frac{\partial p}{\partial x} \right) + \frac{1}{2} \Delta x_-^2 \left(\frac{\partial^2 p}{\partial x^2} \right) - \frac{1}{6} \Delta x_-^3 \left(\frac{\partial^3 p}{\partial x^3} \right) + \frac{1}{24} \Delta x_-^4 \left(\frac{\partial^4 p}{\partial x^4} \right) + \dots \quad (10)$$

Multiplying $p_{i+1,j}$ by Δx_- and $p_{i-1,j}$ by Δx_+ and adding the results, and doing the same for $p_{i,j+1}$ and $p_{i,j-1}$ gives

$$\frac{\partial^2 p}{\partial x^2} = \delta_x^2 p_{i,j} - \frac{1}{12} \left[A \frac{\partial^3 p}{\partial x^3} + B \frac{\partial^4 p}{\partial x^4} \right] + \dots \quad (11)$$

$$\frac{\partial^2 p}{\partial y^2} = \delta_y^2 p_{i,j} - \frac{1}{12} \left[C \frac{\partial^3 p}{\partial y^3} + D \frac{\partial^4 p}{\partial y^4} \right] + \dots \quad (12)$$

where δ_x^2 and δ_y^2 are the centered difference operators for the second derivatives defined as

$$\delta_x^2 p_{i,j} = \frac{2 \Delta x_+ p_{i-1,j} - 2(\Delta x_- + \Delta x_+) p_{i,j} + 2 \Delta x_- p_{i+1,j}}{\Delta x_- \Delta x_+^2 + \Delta x_+ \Delta x_-^2} \quad (13)$$

$$\delta_y^2 p_{i,j} = \frac{2 \Delta y_+ p_{i,j-1} - 2(\Delta y_- + \Delta y_+) p_{i,j} + 2 \Delta y_- p_{i,j+1}}{\Delta y_- \Delta y_+^2 + \Delta y_+ \Delta y_-^2} \quad (14)$$

and the constants A , B , C , and D are defined as

$$A = 4 \frac{\Delta x_- \Delta x_+^3 - \Delta x_+ \Delta x_-^3}{\Delta x_- \Delta x_+^2 + \Delta x_+ \Delta x_-^2}, \quad B = \frac{\Delta x_- \Delta x_+^4 + \Delta x_+ \Delta x_-^4}{\Delta x_- \Delta x_+^2 + \Delta x_+ \Delta x_-^2} \quad (15)$$

$$C = 4 \frac{\Delta y_- \Delta y_+^3 - \Delta y_+ \Delta y_-^3}{\Delta y_- \Delta y_+^2 + \Delta y_+ \Delta y_-^2}, \quad D = \frac{\Delta y_- \Delta y_+^4 + \Delta y_+ \Delta y_-^4}{\Delta y_- \Delta y_+^2 + \Delta y_+ \Delta y_-^2}$$

To have the fourth-order approximations for $\partial^2 p / \partial x^2$ and $\partial^2 p / \partial y^2$, the higher-order partial derivatives in Eqs. (11) and (12) need to be further approximated to be second-order accurate. This operation gives

$$\frac{\partial^3 p}{\partial x^3} = \frac{1}{c_v} \frac{\partial f}{\partial x} - \frac{\partial^3 p}{\partial x \partial y^2}, \quad \frac{\partial^4 p}{\partial x^4} = \frac{1}{c_v} \frac{\partial^2 f}{\partial x^2} - \frac{\partial^4 p}{\partial x^2 \partial y^2} \quad (16)$$

$$\frac{\partial^3 p}{\partial y^3} = \frac{1}{c_v} \frac{\partial f}{\partial y} - \frac{\partial^3 p}{\partial y \partial x^2}, \quad \frac{\partial^4 p}{\partial y^4} = \frac{1}{c_v} \frac{\partial^2 f}{\partial y^2} - \frac{\partial^4 p}{\partial y^2 \partial x^2} \quad (17)$$

Substituting these approximations in Eqs. (11) and (12) and adding the resulting equations gives the desired fourth-order compact scheme (after omitting the error terms) as

$$\delta_x^2 p_{i,j} + \delta_y^2 p_{i,j} + \frac{1}{12} (A \delta_x \delta_y^2 + B \delta_x^2 \delta_y^2 + C \delta_y \delta_x^2 + D \delta_y^2 \delta_x^2) p_{i,j} = \left[\frac{1}{c_v} + \frac{1}{12 c_v} (A \delta_x + B \delta_x^2 + C \delta_y + D \delta_y^2) \right] f_{i,j} \quad (18)$$

where $f_{i,j}$, δ_x and δ_y are given as

$$f_{i,j} = \frac{p_{i,j}^{n+1} - p_{i,j}^n}{\Delta t}$$

$$\delta_x p_{i,j} = \frac{p_{i+1,j} - p_{i-1,j}}{\Delta x_+ + \Delta x_-} \quad (19)$$

$$\delta_y p_{i,j} = \frac{p_{i,j+1} - p_{i,j-1}}{\Delta y_+ + \Delta y_-}$$

The novel high-order ADE scheme for a non-uniform grid is obtained after applying the Crank-Nicolson (1947) technique to Eq. (18) and then arranging the resulting equation into the forward and reverse sweeps as previously shown in Eqs. (2) and (3). This operation gives

Forward sweep

$$u_{i,j}^{n+1} = \alpha_0 u_{i,j}^n + \alpha_1 u_{i-1,j}^{n+1} + \alpha_2 u_{i+1,j}^n + \alpha_3 u_{i,j-1}^{n+1} + \alpha_4 u_{i,j+1}^n + \alpha_5 u_{i-1,j-1}^{n+1} + \alpha_6 u_{i+1,j-1}^n + \alpha_7 u_{i-1,j+1}^{n+1} + \alpha_8 u_{i+1,j+1}^n + \beta_1 (u_{i-1,j}^{n+1} - u_{i-1,j}^n) + \beta_2 (u_{i,j-1}^{n+1} - u_{i,j-1}^n) \quad (20)$$

Reverse sweep

$$v_{i,j}^{n+1} = \alpha_0 v_{i,j}^n + \alpha_1 v_{i-1,j}^n + \alpha_2 v_{i+1,j}^{n+1} + \alpha_3 v_{i,j-1}^n + \alpha_4 v_{i,j+1}^{n+1} + \alpha_5 v_{i-1,j-1}^n + \alpha_6 v_{i+1,j-1}^{n+1} + \alpha_7 v_{i-1,j+1}^n + \alpha_8 v_{i+1,j+1}^{n+1} + \beta_3 (v_{i+1,j}^n - v_{i+1,j}^{n+1}) + \beta_4 (v_{i,j+1}^n - v_{i,j+1}^{n+1}) \quad (21)$$

where α_0 - α_8 and β_1 - β_4 are the grid size-dependent constants. They are given in the Appendix to prevent encumbering the main presentation in the text. Compared to the standard ADE scheme in Eqs. (2) and (3), the new ADE scheme in Eqs. (20) and (21) has more points included in the calculation of the target point, e.g., more diagonal points from the cross-derivatives, due to the fourth-order approximation. For a better visual comparison, the forward sweep from Eq. (20) and the reverse sweep from Eq. (21) are illustrated in Fig. 3a and 3b, respectively.

Fig. 3. Illustration of (a) forward sweep and (b) reverse sweep of the new high-order ADE scheme for non-uniform grid.

From the standpoint of mathematics, convergence is the attribute that the newly-derived ADE scheme must have in order to instill confidence in its results. According to the Lax-Richtmyer equivalence theorem, stability and consistency are the only conditions that must be met for an FD scheme to be called a convergent scheme. Stability means that errors at any stage of the computation decay as the computation progresses, while consistency means that the FD scheme reduces to the original differential equation as the increments in the independent variables vanish. Fortunately, the new ADE scheme has been proven to be stable and consistent, and hence convergent in Prassetyo (2017).

4. EFFICIENT SEQUENTIAL COUPLING TECHNIQUE

For solving coupled problems, the pore pressure solutions from the new ADE scheme will be sequentially coupled

with the geomechanical simulator in FLAC. At every time step, the new ADE scheme will first be executed to solve the fluid flow problem, and then the system will be sequentially brought to geomechanical equilibrium using FLAC's built-in geomechanical simulator. This coupling technique in FLAC is called the sequentially-explicit coupling technique based on the fourth-order ADE scheme, abbreviated as SEA-4. This coupling technique is written in the programming language embedded within FLAC called FISH (Itasca, 2011b). Fig. 4 shows the flow chart of SEA-4 to solve the coupled problems in this paper.

Fig. 4. The proposed SEA-4 coupling technique in FLAC.

The computation starts from a state of geomechanical equilibrium. From this state, the solution to a coupled H-M problem for the next time step ($n + 1$) is obtained sequentially by first solving the flow problem and then the geomechanical problem. When the flow problem is being solved, the displacement field is frozen ($\delta \varepsilon_{vol} = 0$), leaving the fluid-diffusion equation to be solved. The new fourth-order ADE scheme is then called to solve this equation, which will give the pore pressure solution p^{n+1} . Because only the flow problem is solved in this step, the displacement solution is the same as that in the previous time step u^n . The calculated pore pressure solutions are then used as applied loads in the geomechanical calculation by imposing constant fluid mass ($\delta \zeta = 0$). At the end of this geomechanical step, the displacement solution u^{n+1} is obtained. Several geomechanical steps may be taken to bring the system to equilibrium before the computation progresses to the next time step. This sequential procedure is then repeated until the desired simulation time is reached.

In the following sections, the accuracy and efficiency of SEA-4 will be compared to FLAC's built-in coupled

technique that uses the embedded fluid flow scheme, which is conditionally stable and requires that the fluid time step must be smaller than a critical value (Itasca, 2011a). The merit of SEA-4 is that it removes this time step restriction, yielding an efficient H-M simulation without suffering from numerical instability while still maintaining high numerical accuracy.

5. VALIDATION AGAINST TERZAGHI'S CONSOLIDATION

SEA-4 is first validated against the one-dimensional consolidation of a soil column known as Terzaghi's consolidation. A soil column of height $H = 24$ m and width $W = 6$ m is loaded by a constant stress of $p_o = 100$ kPa on the surface (Fig. 5). The base of the column is fixed and the lateral displacements are restricted. The bottom, left, and right boundaries are impermeable while the top boundary is fully drained. The material properties for Terzaghi's consolidation are given in Table 1. The simulation is carried out for a total consolidation time of $t = 6$ days, corresponding to a normalized consolidation time of $t^* = 10$ ($t^* = c_v t / H^2$). The time step used in SEA-4 is $\Delta t = 1.0$ s, while that in FLAC's basic scheme is $\Delta t_{crit} = 0.05$ s (the critical value to maintain its stability).

Fig. 5. FLAC grid for Terzaghi's 1-D consolidation problem.

Table 1. Material properties for Terzaghi's consolidation

Material properties	Value
Hydraulic conductivity, k_H (m/s)	$1.0 \cdot 10^{-6}$
Porosity, ϕ	0.375
Shear modulus, G (Pa)	$4.0 \cdot 10^7$
Drained bulk modulus, K (Pa)	$6.7 \cdot 10^7$

Fig. 6 shows the histories of pore pressure and vertical displacement at the monitored locations, while Fig. 7 shows the profiles of pore pressure and vertical displacement along the column height at various consolidation times. In all figures, the results from SEA-4 are nearly identical with the analytical solutions. The maximum absolute errors in SEA-4 compared to the analytical solutions are on average only 6% for the pore pressure and 0.4% for the displacement. These errors are relatively small considering the large time step size used in SEA-4 for this problem, which is 20 times the time step size used in FLAC's coupled scheme. SEA-4 is able to reduce the computer runtime by 40%, from 585 s in the fully-coupled approach in FLAC to only 354 s in SEA-4.

Fig. 6. History of (a) pore pressure and (b) vertical degree of consolidation versus log time.

Fig. 7. Profile of (a) pore pressure and (b) vertical displacement with column height at various consolidation times.

6. TUNNEL UNDER SURFACE LOADING

The potential application of SEA-4 in rock engineering is now demonstrated by simulating the H-M response of a permeable tunnel under surface loading. This problem is inspired by real engineering problems in which many high-rise buildings in urban areas are constructed over existing underground structures, such as railway stations, metro tunnels, utility tunnels, and so forth. Some examples are the fourteen-story building that was built above Sydney's underground Green Square Station (Nye, 2005) and the twin-tower skyscraper complex that was built on top of the old Rotterdam Central railway station (Zigterman, 2006). These cases show that it is imperative that the design of underground spaces in urban areas

account for the load of the current overburden and future surface loads. The tunnel problem in this paper is taken from published reports (Prasetyo, 2017; Prasetyo and Gutierrez, 2016a, 2016b).

The tunnel is built in FLAC under the plane-strain condition as a 12 m by 15 m horseshoe-shaped tunnel that is externally loaded with a surface pressure of 0.25 MPa over a width of 30 m. The amount of the pressure corresponds to half of the ground pressure imposed by the Empire State Building. The model boundary was 100 m by 300 m, with the tunnel located 30 m below the groundwater table. Due to the assumption of vertical symmetry in the problem, only half of the problem was modeled (Fig. 8). However, to plot the full settlement profile, the other half of the model is projected symmetrically based on the side being modeled. The pore pressure is free to change at the left, far-field, and bottom boundaries but fixed at zero at the top of the model and at the tunnel boundary.

Fig. 8. Cross-section of the FLAC tunnel model.

The properties of weathered granite and unreinforced concrete liner are used for the ground and liner, respectively (Table 2). The Mohr-Coulomb yield criterion is assigned as the ground constitutive model, while a linearly elastic relationship is assigned to the liner. These properties are common in numerical studies of urban tunneling (Itasca, 2011c; Rocscience, 2016; Shin et al., 2002; Xie et al., 2016).

Table 2. Material properties for granite and liner

Properties	Granite	Liner	Unit
Density	2500	2500	kg/m ³
Young's modulus	1000	35,000	MPa
Poisson's ratio	0.28	0.17	-
Cohesion	0.2	-	MPa
Friction angle	45	-	...°
Hydraulic conductivity	1 · 10 ⁻¹¹	-	m/s
Thickness	-	0.6	m
Compressive yield strength	-	45	MPa
Tensile yield strength	-	4.5	MPa

The excavation and the H-M simulation procedures are conducted through the following steps:

- Step 1: Tunnel excavation.** From the initial in situ stresses, the tunnel excavation begins and the tunnel tractions are relaxed by 50%.
- Step 2: Liner installation.** The liner is now installed and the tunnel tractions are relaxed completely around the tunnel. The permeable tunnel is imposed by fixing the pore pressures at the tunnel boundary at zero. The coupled H-M simulation is carried out for a total of 10 years before the embankment load is applied.
- Step 3: Embankment loading.** The embankment load is applied by progressive application of a surface pressure of 0.25 MPa on a 30 m section of the model top boundary. During this step, no flow is assumed to take place (undrained simulation). Pore pressures will generate because of the induced deformations but do not dissipate.
- Step 4: Steady state.** To reach steady state, the coupled H-M simulation is then carried out again for a total of 30 years, which is the characteristic time for the diffusion process of this problem (i.e., the time needed for the generated pore pressure during embankment loading to dissipate during consolidation).

Fig. 9 provides the contour plots of the induced H-M response of the surrounding ground after the surface loading is applied. As one can see, the comparison between SEA-4 and FLAC for the contours of horizontal (Fig. 9a) and vertical displacements (Fig. 9b) as well as of the pore pressure (Fig. 9c) is very satisfactory. Fig. 10 shows the induced thrust (Fig. 10a) and moments (Fig. 10b) in the liner after surface loading and at steady state. The agreement between SEA-4 and FLAC is also excellent. Similarly, satisfactory comparison is also observed on the profile of the surface settlement in Fig. 11. In addition, SEA-4 can also mimic the increase in the pore pressure due to the surface loading and the subsequent pore pressure dissipation towards the steady state (Fig. 12). Similar behavior can also be observed for the history of tunnel convergence and tunnel closure with time (Fig. 13).

In this tunnel problem, SEA-4 uses $\Delta t = 3$ days while FLAC uses $\Delta t_{\text{cri}} = 0.2$ day. In terms of computational efficiency, because a larger time step is used, SEA-4 is able to reduce computer runtime by 24% from 22 minutes in FLAC to 18 minutes in SEA-4.

While further H-M simulations may be needed to fully exploit the efficiency and accuracy of SEA-4, the results

in this paper show that SEA-4 holds great promise for long-term and large-scale coupled H-M problems even when an irregular grid is used. Future work should attempt to couple SEA-4 with shear behavior of rock joints for H-M analysis of tunneling in fractured saturated rock (Prasetyo et al., 2017) and to couple the new ADE scheme with other existing geomechanical simulators to widen its application.

Fig. 9. Contour of (a) horizontal displacement, (b) vertical displacement, and (c) pore pressure after surface loading.

Fig. 10. Profile of the induced (a) thrust and (b) moment after surface loading and at steady state.

Fig. 11. Profile of settlement (a) after surface loading and (b) at steady state.

Fig. 12. History of pore pressure at the (a) crown, (b) springline, and (c) invert vs. consolidation time.

7. CONCLUSIONS

Explicit techniques have been used for simulating coupled fluid flow and geomechanical interactions in porous media. However, the techniques are conditionally stable and require small time steps, affecting their efficiency for long-term simulations.

To remove this restriction, this study developed an unconditionally stable high-order ADE scheme for a non-uniform grid capable of solving flow problems in plane strain conditions. The resulting pore pressure solutions from the new ADE scheme were sequentially coupled with the geomechanical simulator in FLAC. This coupling technique is called the sequentially-explicit coupling technique based on the fourth-order ADE scheme, abbreviated as SEA-4.

Validation against Terzaghi's consolidation showed that SEA-4 reduced computer runtimes by 40% compared to FLAC's basic scheme without numerical instability.

Fig. 13. History of tunnel convergence at the (a) crown, (b) invert, and (c) total closure vs. consolidation time.

Furthermore, compared to the analytical solutions, SEA-4 only induced average errors of 6% for pore pressure and 0.4% for displacement solutions.

In addition, SEA-4 was used to simulate the H-M response of a permeable tunnel under surface loading and was able to reduce computer runtime by 24%. Simulation results showed that the comparison of the induced H-M response of the ground surrounding the tunnel between SEA-4 and FLAC was very satisfactory. The contour of H-M response of the surrounding ground and the profile of the induced structural response in the liner are acceptably represented. The history of pore pressure and displacement in SEA-4 were also in close agreement with those in FLAC. SEA-4 was able to mimic the pore pressure and convergence increase due to the surface loading and the subsequent pore pressure dissipation and continuous deformation towards the steady state.

The results in this paper suggest that the newly derived high-order ADE scheme is valid and that it will open

avenues for accurate and efficient simulation of the H-M interaction in porous media. For solving larger rock engineering problems, future work may include coupling SEA-4 with shear behavior of rock joints for H-M analysis of fractured saturated ground and coupling the new ADE scheme with other existing geomechanical simulators to widen its application.

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APPENDIX

Grid size-dependent constants for higher-order plane strain ADE scheme

$$\begin{aligned}
\alpha_0 &= \frac{\alpha_N}{\alpha_D} = \frac{1 - r \Delta t \left[\frac{1}{2}(a+b+c+d) - \frac{1}{2} \frac{1}{12}(B+D)(a+b)(c+d) - \frac{1}{2} \frac{1}{6}(B(a+b)+D(c+d)) \right]}{1 + r \Delta t \left[\frac{1}{2}(a+b+c+d) - \frac{1}{2} \frac{1}{12}(B+D)(a+b)(c+d) - \frac{1}{2} \frac{1}{6}(B(a+b)+D(c+d)) \right]} \\
\alpha_1 &= r \frac{\Delta t}{\alpha_D} \left[a + \frac{1}{12}(Ah_x - a(B+D))(c+d) \right] & \alpha_2 &= r \frac{\Delta t}{\alpha_D} \left[b - \frac{1}{12}(Ah_x + b(B+D))(c+d) \right] \\
\alpha_3 &= r \frac{\Delta t}{\alpha_D} \left[c + \frac{1}{12}(Ch_y - c(B+D))(a+b) \right] & \alpha_4 &= r \frac{\Delta t}{\alpha_D} \left[d - \frac{1}{12}(Ch_y + d(B+D))(a+b) \right] \\
\alpha_5 &= \frac{r}{12} \frac{\Delta t}{\alpha_D} [ac(B+D) - aCh_y - cAh_x] & \alpha_6 &= \frac{r}{12} \frac{\Delta t}{\alpha_D} [bc(B+D) - bCh_y + cAh_x] \\
\alpha_7 &= \frac{r}{12} \frac{\Delta t}{\alpha_D} [ad(B+D) + aCh_y - dAh_x] & \alpha_8 &= \frac{r}{12} \frac{\Delta t}{\alpha_D} [bd(B+D) + bCh_y + dAh_x] \\
\beta_1 &= \frac{1}{6\alpha_D} [Ah_x - Bh_x] & \beta_2 &= \frac{1}{6\alpha_D} [Ch_y - Dc] \\
\beta_3 &= \frac{1}{6\alpha_D} [Ah_x + Bh_y] & \beta_4 &= \frac{1}{6\alpha_D} [Ch_y + Dd] \\
a &= \frac{2\Delta x_+}{\Delta x_- \Delta x_+^2 + \Delta x_+ \Delta x_-^2} & b &= \frac{2\Delta x_-}{\Delta x_- \Delta x_+^2 + \Delta x_+ \Delta x_-^2} & h_x &= \frac{1}{\Delta x_+ + \Delta x_-} \\
c &= \frac{2\Delta y_+}{\Delta y_- \Delta y_+^2 + \Delta y_+ \Delta y_-^2} & d &= \frac{2\Delta y_-}{\Delta y_- \Delta y_+^2 + \Delta y_+ \Delta y_-^2} & h_y &= \frac{1}{\Delta y_+ + \Delta y_-}
\end{aligned} \tag{A.1}$$